

THE ROLE OF DEICTIC EXPRESSIONS IN CONTEXT

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Annotation Deixis belongs to the area of pragmatics because it directly involves the relationship between the structure of language and the context in which it is used. This article will discuss deictic expressions, firstly by giving definitions by different linguists, secondly by presenting and discussing the different deictic categories and finally by commenting on the different types of uses of deictic expressions such as deictic and anaphoric.

Keywords: Anaphoric, Deictic Expressions, Deixis, Personal Deixis, Spatial Deixis, Temporal Deixis, Discourse Deixis, Social Deixis.

Аннотация Дейксис принадлежит к области прагматики, потому что он непосредственно затрагивает отношения между структурой языка и контекстом, в котором он используется. В этой статье мы обсудим дейктические выражения, во-первых, дав определения разных лингвистов, во-вторых, представляя и обсуждая различные дейктические категории и, наконец, комментируя различные типы использования дейктических выражений, таких как дейктические и анафорические.

Ключевые слова: анафорические, дейктические выражения, дейксис, дейксис личностный, дейксис пространственный, дейксис временной, дейксис дискурсивный, дейксис социальный.

A deictic expression (deictic from Ancient Greek δεικτικός, deiktikós, 'capable of proof') is defined as any word or expression used to indicate the place, time, and the condition or situation of the speaker at the time of speaking. Deictic expressions (also

referred to as 'deictics') will typically include personal pronouns, demonstratives, verbs, and adverbs.

Deixis is an important field studied in pragmatics, semantics and linguistics. Deixis refers to the phenomenon wherein understanding the meaning of certain words and phrases in an utterance requires contextual information. Words or phrases that require contextual information to convey meaning are deictic [6, p 54].

The contextual information of the utterance mentioned by Levinson consists of information about the speaker, the addressee, the time and the place. For example, if we take a close look on the sentence *I am leaving tomorrow*, who does *I*, *am*, and *tomorrow* refer to? We cannot identify the meaning of this utterance, unless we know the time of the utterance, the place, and who the speaker is, in other words the context of the utterance. Expressions like *I*, *you*, *we*, *this*, *that*, *here*, *there*, *today*, *tomorrow*, are all indexed, and the listener needs to identify the speaker, the time and the place of the utterance to fully understand what is being said and meant.

There are three deictic categories identified in the literature. These are: **personal deixis** (*I*, *you*, *we*), **spatial deixis** (*this*, *that*, *here*, *there*), and **temporal deixis** (*now*, *today*, *yesterday*). In addition to person, place and time deixis, Levinson, following Lyons and Filmore, adds two other deictic categories. These are: **social deixis** which covers the encoding of social distinctions that are relative to participant-roles, particularly aspects of the social relationship holding between speaker and addressee(s) or speaker and some referents, and **discourse deixis** which involves the encoding of reference to portions of the unfolding discourse in which the utterance is located.

However, Yule describes deixis as a way of “pointing through language”, and also refers to deixis as a technical word that comes from Greek. Yule also admits that deictic expressions have their most basic uses in face-to-face spoken utterances. In addition, Lyons has defined deixis as follows:

By deixis is meant the location and identification of persons, objects, events, processes and activities talked about, or referred to, in relation to the spatio-temporal

context created and sustained by the act of utterance and the participation in it, typically, of a single speaker and a least one addressee [7, p 377].

In other words, an utterance containing deictic expressions such as *I will take this paper over here* requires contextual information for an accurate meaning: which *paper* is being referred to, knowledge about space – knowing where *here* is, and who the speaker is. Levinson states that an utterance can be tested as being deictic or not in terms of its truth conditions. For example, if we say *John is the husband of Mary*, the utterance can be either true or false, however if we say *He is the husband of Mary*, we cannot assess whether the sentence is true or false because it depends who the *he* is. If we take another example, such as *I'll come and see you tomorrow*, we cannot assess whether this sentence is true or false because we are not aware of when the sentence was written, therefore we do not know when *tomorrow* is. Thus, knowledge about the context in the interpretation of utterances containing deictic expressions is crucial.

For Levinson [6, p 64], deixis is organised in an egocentric way, with the deictic centre constituting the reference point in relation to which a deictic expression is to be interpreted. For example, in an utterance such as *I'm over here now*, the speaker, the actual location and the actual time of the utterance are respectively the deictic centres. The term deictic centre underlines that the deictic term has to relate to the situation exactly at the point where the utterance is made or the text is written, in other words it has to relate to the position from which the deictic terms are understood. In conversations, the deictic centre is constantly changing between the partners; the speech event is conceptualised from a different point of view.

A deictic expression is a word or phrase, that points out the different meaning in various situations. Without a pragmatic approach, the interpretation of an utterance would be impossible to understand, therefore deictic expressions are crucial and it involves the relationship between the structure of languages and the contexts in which they are used. A word that depends on deictic indicators is called a deictic word, and is bound to a context. Hence, words that are deictic hold a

denotational meaning which varies depending on time and/or place, and a fixed semantic meaning.

In addition to knowing the time, place and the speaker and addressee, deictic expressions help us realise what is close to the speaker and what is not. This is defined by the following two terms: proximal (near the speaker), such as *this, here, now*, and distal (away from the speaker) such as *that, there, then* [6, p 396]. This concept of distance is more relevant to the study of spatial deixis. Deictic expressions also help us realise if the movement is away from the speaker or towards the speaker (*go vs come*). According to Fillmore (1977), the most obvious manifestations of deictic categories in languages are to be found in the systems of pronouns i.e *I, we, she*, demonstratives i.e *this, these*; and tenses i.e *walk, walked*.

Person deixis localises an entity in relation to the position of the speaker and/or hearer [3, p 356]. First and second person pronouns typically refer to the speaking and hearing speech participants, whereas third person pronouns designate the non-speech or narrated participant. According to Lyons the active participants are the speaker and the addressee, whereas the third person is not an active participant in the speech act.

To give an illustration of what I mean let us look at the following examples:

I was busy.

You came late.

I saw *her*.

Third person pronouns may be used deictically or anaphorically. An anaphoric use of a deictic expression occurs when reference is being made to another entity that was introduced earlier in the text/speech.

Examples:

George thinks *she* is happy. (deictic use)

Ann thinks I heard *her*. (anaphoric use)

In English, pronouns come in singular and plural forms, several are marked for case, and the third person singular forms encode gender.

Another category of deixis is spatial deixis. Spatial deixis localises both the speech participants and the narrated participants in space. The most frequent words are the pronouns *this/that* and *these/those* . Other expressions that belong to this category are the adverbs *here/there* and prepositions *in/on*.

Spatial deixis also entails whether something is near the speaker or not (*this* vs *that*). In all languages, there are pairs of verbs such as *come/go* , *bring/take*, which are interpreted to identify the direction of the motion, towards or away from the place of speech event, hence the spatial deixis is the marking in language of the orientation or position in a space. Lyons [7, p 648] states that “there are two ways in which we can identify an object by means of a referring expression: first, by informing the addressee where it is; second, by telling him what is like, what the properties it has or what class of objects it belongs to”.

Fillmore talks about the fact that deictic pointing can be achieved in different ways. He distinguishes between two types of uses: the gestural and symbolic ones. The gestural use requires monitoring the speech event in order to identify the referent, whereas the symbolic use involves activating knowledge about the communicative situation and the referent. Levinson exemplifies the two uses with the following examples:

This finger hurts (gestural).

This city stinks (symbolic).

In the first example, we notice that the demonstrative can be accompanied by a pointing gesture which illustrates the gestural use. In the second example, which does not involve a pointing gesture and shows a larger situational context illustrates the symbolic use.

Temporal deixis is another category of deictic expressions. It refers to an event of an utterance, which takes place any time relative to the speaking time and is, therefore, represented by tense, time adverbials and sometimes by spatial prepositions such as *in the morning*, *at night*, *on time*. The location of an event referred to and represented by time and tense constitutes the deictic centre in the utterance of a speaker. In English, the present and the past are morphologically

marked. Morphology is an area of study within grammar that describes how words are composed. A linguistic element is morphologically marked when it is more distinctively identified than another element, by adding a morpheme. A morpheme is the minimal unit of meaning. For example, the first person present tense *I clean* is not morphologically marked. On the other hand, the third person *he clean-s*, and the past tense *he clean-ed* are marked by the morpheme *-s* and *-ed*. The future is constructed using the modal verb *will*. Another way to express the future in English is by attaching an adverb of time indicating the future illustrated in the following example:

I go on holiday *next week*.

She *drinks* coffee *every morning* (morphologically marked present tense *-s*, expressing an event occurring on a regular basis)

Fillmore (1977) and Levinson (1983) note that the deictic words *yesterday*, *today*, and *tomorrow*, pre-empt the absolute ways of referring to the relevant days. Thus, the utterance, *I will call you on Sunday*, said on Sunday, can only be referring to next Sunday, otherwise the speaker should have said today.

Having presented the traditional deictic categories, what will now be discussed is the discourse and the social deixis. The discourse deixis provides a reference to an utterance backward or forward to other utterances. Levinson [6, p 62] states that discourse deixis is “the encoding of reference to portions of the unfolding discourse in which the utterance is located”. In other words, discourse deixis refers to all expressions and phrases that point the reader or hearer through spoken or written text. These examples illustrate discourse deixis: *earlier*, *later*, *the preceding x*, *the following s*, *in the following paragraphs*, *in the following weeks*, *during next month*, *in the next chapter*.

Social deixis refers to the relation between the speaker and the addressee and third party referents. According to Levinson social deixis is those aspects of language structure that are anchored to the social identities of participants in the speech event, or to relations between them, or to relations between them and other referents [6, p 63]. In some languages, such as Spanish, French, Romanian, the

singular second person pronoun has two forms: *tu* and *usted - vous-dumneavoastra*. The first form (*tu*) is used to address to a speaker in an informal or relaxed way. The second form (*usted – vous – dumneavoastra*) is used in a more formal or polite context. In Modern English, there is no such distinction for the second person pronoun *you*. However, in the Elizabethan English *thee*, an archaic pronoun has been widely used with the same role as *vous* in French [5, p 27].

I tell *Thee* what Antonio, I love *Thee*, and it is my love that speaks [4].

There are some expressions that are not understood unless the interlocutors have some knowledge about the context of the utterance, knowledge about the status of those involved, intend of the speaker, the place and time of the utterance. These words do not have a constant meaning, and they are known as deictic words. Deictic words are a crucial element of pragmatics because they are related to the context of the utterance.

To sum up, personal deixis system in English marks distinctions in gender (in the third person only) and number (in first and third person); the second person pronoun *you* can refer to both singular and plural entities, i.e. neutralised. Thus, personal deixis can mark a number of overlapping distinctions: person, gender, number, and social status. Spatial deixis involves the specification of locations relative to points of reference in the speech event. English has a proximal or distal distance from speaker. A third type of deixis is temporal deixis which shows the orientation or position of the referent of actions and events in time. As shown in temporal deixis section, the concept of time English is represented by three main classes: time adverbials, tenses, and time expressions. These three categories of deixis are known as traditional deictic categories. Furthermore, Fillmore identified two more categories: discourse and social deixis. Discourse deixis indicates or refers to some portion or aspect of the ongoing discourse, and the social deixis reflects the social relation between the speakers, and classifiers used with human referents.

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